

Revitalization and Synthesis of Factors Associated with the Purchase of Local Fast Moving Consumer Goods: The Zambian Perspective

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Abstract:- Globalization as a concept has brought many benefits to countries as it has enhanced the linkage between different economies. However, preferring to ignore the detrimental consequences of globalization can harm the nation's regional economy. Local citizens' ability to support local products should be supported through buy-local campaigns that help the expansion of the economy and local manufacturing sectors. The increased levels of unemployment in many countries including Zambia can just be reduced by encouraging the purchase of local FMCG's by local customers. This, therefore, requires understanding the factors associated with the purchase of the local brands. In Zambia, customers of FMCG's prefer imported brands as compared to local ones. The factors that affects consumer behavior in Zambia are; quality, packaging, accessibility, and price.

Keywords:- Awareness; Branding; Globalization; FMCG's; Quality.

I. INTRODUCTION

In the era of globalization, many companies in different countries have embarked on a robust action to expand their market globally. Globalization is seen as one of the major challenges that companies encounter nowadays (Burgess & Steenkamp, 2013; Khanna, Palepu & Sinha, 2005). It has evidently been observed that in some countries, domestic consumers tend to be more ethnocentric and patriotic as they mostly prefer local products to imported ones. This preference can unequivocally be attributed to their demonstration of love for their country. However, in some instances, the consumer might forgo their ethnocentrism and patriotism to get the best value for their money. It has often been said and believed that the availability of choice might change the consumers' minds. Thus, in a Zambian case, although she is producing her own products, there are quite a number of Zambians who prefer buying imported goods or products to local ones. It is worth mentioning that most developing countries are still grappling with the behavior and attitude of citizens of not supporting their own locally produced FMCG's. However, matters and concerns to do with the origins of the products to be bought, and the

transparency of the retail outlets also has proven to be of interest to consumers owing to their growing awareness of environmental and health-related concerns (Delaney & McCarthy, 2011; Rainbolt *et al.*, 2012). Many countries world over, have realized that encouraging consumers to buy local products has many great benefits to a country such as; the provision of employment to the locals, improved payment of taxes which helps governments meet their obligations and improves the support by corporate companies to the communities (Ekanem, Mafuyai, & Clardy, 2013).

II. THE STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

The concept of globalization has brought many benefits to countries as it has become easier to have business linkages without much challenge. However, deliberating deciding to go blink on the negative effects of globalization might injure the country's local economy. The growth of the local manufacturing industries should be translated into the growth of the economy and subsequently support livelihood to the local citizens. Has globalization positively helped some developing countries such as Zambia? The Zamstat report enumerated the rate of unemployment which arguably has been said to have reached an alarming level of 13.20% in 2019 from 11.40% in 2018 (Zamstat, 2020). Although Trading Economics (2022) asserts that there was a reduction in unemployment from 13.20% in 2019 to 12.20 in 2020, this is still unacceptably high. According to Mweemba (2022), many consumers of FMCG's in Zambia prefer imported brands as opposed to locally manufactured products. This could be as a result of lack of synthesis in the marketing efforts. A study by Darku and Akpan (2020) acknowledged the damage imported brands have on the local manufacturing industries. The continued support of imported products in Zambia happens at a time when Zambia is grappling with the rise in unemployment levels.

III. OBJECTIVES

- To establish the level of consumer awareness about the importance of buying local products.
- To investigate the effectiveness of the promotional strategies used by local manufacturers and distributors.

IV. HYPOTHESIS

H₀: The level of awareness by the consumers of FMCG's doesn't have any influence on the consumer's support of local FMCG's in Zambia.

H₁: The level of awareness by the consumers of FMCG's has influence on the consumer's support of local FMCG's in Zambia.

H₀: The promotional strategies used by manufacturers and distributors don't have an influence on the consumer support of the local FMCG's in Zambia.

H₂: The promotional strategies used by manufacturers and distributors have an influence on the consumer support of the local FMCG's in Zambia.

V. LITERATURE REVIEW

Any company that conducts business must increase consumer awareness and offer them benefits in order to persuade them to buy a product and possibly become loyal. One sign that a product has strong brand recognition is when consumers can recall or recognize it. When deciding what to buy, a customer's capacity to recognize or recall a brand is crucial. According to several studies, businesses can only improve customer loyalty, preference, and buy intentions by raising consumer knowledge (Hsieh, 2016; Monareh, 2012). Because of this, brand recognition influences consumer choices through brand associations, and effective branding supports marketing efforts (Noorlitaria, Pangestu, Surapati, & Mahsyar, 2020).

According to Fajariah, Thoyib, & Rahman (2016), brand awareness refers to how aware a customer is of a product and how likely they are to purchase it. Governments and businesses have promoted the purchase of local products among consumers through a variety of marketing initiatives mostly under the umbrella of campaigns called buy local campaigns. Easy local product recognition assures that a consumer will continue to support a specific product. Ilmiyati (2011) postulates that enhanced product awareness has a favorable and considerable influence on brand loyalty. The study by Kurniati, Farida, & Nurseto (2013) was in agreement with the findings of Ilmiyati (2011), stating that increasing brand awareness is essential for boosting consumer loyalty to a local brand.

Lu, Gursoy, & Lu (2015) assert that brand awareness and brand loyalty have a significant relationship. Aulia (2015) conducted a study on the relationship between brand awareness and brand loyalty, and the findings also found a strong relationship between the two variables. According to Sanjaya (2013), brand awareness affects perceived quality. All these studies underscore that brand awareness has a positive correlation with customer loyalty.

According to William & Japariato (2016), a brand with strong brand recognition and a favorable reputation will encourage customer brand loyalty, and the greater the brand awareness, the greater the brand trust, which further encourages consumer purchase intentions. According to Monareh & Wirawan (2012), customer knowledge of a

brand or campaign directly influences their intent to purchase the products.

A. Effectiveness of the promotional strategies used for local brands

Buy-local campaigns can only be a complete success if they are completely backed by an effective integrated communications mix to raise consumer awareness. Many well-known "Buy Local" campaigns have focused on promoting a single product line for the benefit of the community (Salehudin, 2016), with the agriculture product category seeing the most noticeable campaigning, with an emphasis on neighbors exchanging local goods (Insch, Prentice, & Knight, 2011). According to Kaushik (2011), the campaigns for local products can be effective if there is a good exposure to the targeted audience.

The goal of the purchase local campaign is to educate local consumers about the value of supporting homegrown businesses. Darku & Akpan (2020) discovered that just 14.4% of respondents in South Africa and 55.8% in Ghana were exposed to the campaign on a regular basis, translating to an average mean of 2.18 for South Africa and 4.05 for Ghana respectively. A study was conducted in Oman with the primary goal of determining the influence of customer behavior as shown in the media on brand awareness by looking at a number of variables, including price, quality, brand, promotion, and offers. The report's findings indicated that local brand recognition was positively impacted by both social media and traditional media alike (Salim, Jahdhami, & Handhali, 2017). The Omani academics thought that deliberate and active exposure through the use of powerful media should be employed to increase consumer preference and awareness for indigenous FMCG products.

Studies on how to help local brands more effectively by enhancing local campaigns have been conducted. Empirical data reveals that raising customer knowledge and preference for local FMCG's is crucial if the industry players are to encourage or foster customer loyalty (Pradhan & Misra, 2014; Daphne & Fernandes, 2014). According to a study by Salim, Jahdhami, & Handhali (2017), advertising through efficient media is very effective way to educate local consumers about the value of purchasing local FMCG products. Salehudin (2016) claims that a lot of nations invested much in mass advertising to raise consumer awareness of the value of supporting local brands. This was done in an effort to increase the competitiveness of local brands.

B. Implementing advertising in the buy local campaign

According to Insch, Prentice, & Knight (2011), the use of advertising in the implementation of the "buy local" campaign has an overall positive impact on domestic customers' ability to support local goods. Salehudin (2016) adds that the research on the 100% Buy Local campaign that was done in Indonesia demonstrated the significant effects of effective advertising in influencing consumers to choose domestic brands over foreign ones. The Fara Research Report (2018) found that Ghana buy local campaign also employed national talk programs on radio and television to

inform customers. The major goal of Proudly South African and Buy Local in Ghana was to raise consumer awareness of the value of purchasing locally made products rather than those that are imported.

Even though consumers in Ghana didn't seem to be as aware of the campaign as they were in South Africa, the study by Darku & Akpan (2020) revealed that the Ghanaian buy local promotional campaign was nevertheless more successful. The visibility score for both campaigns was 3.14 on average. In comparison to the average, South Africa's awareness level was lower (2.18), whereas Ghana's knowledge level was greater (2.18). According to the study, in the case of Ghana, 31.5% of awareness was spread through TV programs, 58.2% through referrals, and 43.8% through radio presentations. On the other hand, in the South African situation, it was discovered that television (39.3%) was the most popular source of information on the campaign, followed by the internet (37.5%), referrals (28.6%), and radio (19.6%). However, it is unknown as to which media platform is used in Zambia and how effective it is.

The same study revealed that the media vehicles utilized in Ghana and South Africa had different strengths. In Ghana, radio and referrals were quite effective, but in South Africa, television and the internet were effective. Darku & Akpan (2020) focused on the selling culture and the impact of the "buy local" movement in the textile industries of Ghana and South Africa.

VI. THEORETICAL FRAMEWORK

A. The 5 'A's Model (Kotler, Kartajaya, & Setiawan, 2016)

The common and famous AIDA model was updated by Rucker (2016), as cited in Kotler, Kartajaya, & Setiawan (2016), with what he referred to as the four A's: awareness, attitude, act, and act again. This framework adds a new stage called act again and condensed the interest and desire stages into an attitude. In the last stage, act attempts to gauge client retention once more since it sees repeat purchases as a powerful indicator of consumer loyalty. Kotler, Kartajaya, & Setiawan's (2016) is better suitable for buy local campaigns

like the Proudly Zambian Campaign since it predicts the likely behavior of customers in terms of their acting as brand ambassadors (Rucker, 2016).

The Five A's model reflects a change in the consumer route brought about by the digital era, as suggested by Kotler, Kartajaya, & Setiawan (2016). The process from awareness to advocacy does not necessarily have to occur in the order Wijaya suggests in this age of connectedness (2011). Understanding customer attitudes can be challenging because a customer's response to an advertisement is the result of a learned predisposition. Kotler, Kartajaya, & Setiawan, (2016) proposed the following model; awareness, appeal, ask, act, and advocate. In the age of connectivity, customer loyalty is defined as the customer's willingness to generate strong recommendations in favor of the advertised brand or product. As a result, a satisfied customer may engage in brand advocacy and recommend it to others.

VII. METHODOLOGY

Langos (2004) defined methodology as the structure related with a specific arrangement of paradigmatic suppositions that one uses to conduct a study, for example, the scientific method, ethnography and activity research. For this study, the researcher used a survey. According to Check and Schutt (2012), survey research is the collection of information from a sample of individuals gotten from a large population. For this study, the population of interest was the consumers of FMCG's in Lusaka. The questionnaire was used to collect the data. Data analysis was conducted using SPSS to come up with descriptive information.

A. Sampling Strategy

Sampling is a process of choosing a representative group of people or items from the population of interest in order to generalize the findings (Etikan and Bala, 2017). For this study, the researcher used probability (systematic) sampling method, of which quantitative data was collected from consumers of FMCG's in Lusaka District of Zambia. The sample involved 295 respondents.

VIII. DATA ANALYSIS

Level of awareness by consumers of Fast Moving Consumer Goods about the Promotional campaign supporting local brands					
		Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid	Strongly Agree	21	7.2	7.2	7.2
	Agree	66	22.6	22.6	29.8
	Neutral	41	14.0	14.0	43.8
	Disagree	42	14.4	14.4	58.2
	Strongly Disagree	122	41.8	41.8	100.0
	Total	292	100.0	100.0	

Table 1:- Level of Customer Awareness

Table 1 above shows the summary descriptive findings on the level of awareness by consumers of FMCG’s about the Proudly Zambian Campaign supporting the consumption of locally produced brands. 7.2% strongly agreed to be aware of the campaign, 22.6% agreed and 14.0% were neutral. 14.4% disagreed and 41.8% strongly disagreed about being aware of the campaign. A comparative study by Darku &

Akpan (2020) had its findings showing that the average score for awareness was 3.14. South Africa had a lower awareness level than the average (2.18), whilst Ghana had a higher awareness level than the average (4.05). However, the average mean for the level of awareness by consumers about the PZC is 2.39 which is skewed to strongly disagree.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
On TV	85	29.1	29.1	29.1
On Radio	14	4.8	4.8	33.9
Billboard	23	7.9	7.9	41.8
Newspaper	10	3.4	3.4	45.2
Non	160	54.8	54.8	100.0
Total	292	100.0	100.0	

Table 2:- Media Used to Ensure Message Visibility

29.1% of local customers saw the campaign on TV and 4.8% heard the information through national Radio. 7.9% of respondents saw the campaign on Billboards, 3.4% of respondents saw the campaign in the Newspapers (press) and 54.8% had never seen the campaign anywhere. This there confirms that the buy local campaign is not effective as the message is seen being delivered to the customers of FMCG’s through the media vehicles such as radio, TV, Newspaper and Billboards. A study by Darku & Akpan (2020) present different results to the current study; in South Africa, 39.3% of respondents accessed the local campaign on TV, 37.5%

from the Internet, 19.6% from Radio, 25% from Newspapers and 28.6% from friends. In Ghana, referrals from friends was represented by 58.2% of respondents, 43.8% from Radio, 31.5% from TV, 16.4% from Newspapers and 11.6% from Internet. It can be deduced that the reason behind the success of the Ghanaian campaign could be as a result of the information being shared through referrals signifying that the buy local campaign had struck the chord with the Ghanaian citizens as they were more ready to act as local brand crusaders (Darku & Akpan, 2020).

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Local	61	20.9	20.9	20.9
Foreign	231	79.1	79.1	100.0
Total	292	100.0	100.0	

Table 3:- The FMCG’s Customers Prefer

20.9% prefer buying local brands, while 79.1% prefer buying foreign or imported FMCG’s. In table 4 below, the results show that respondents buy imported FMCG’s due to quality (50%), accessibility (12%) and packaging (11%). These results suggest that customers do not support the local brands due to poor quality, unavailability and poor packaging. The campaign can still not be successful if the

local FMCG’s are of unacceptable quality. According to the study by Van den Berg (2017) in South Africa, 24% of the respondents strongly disagreed to a statement that buying foreign brands is un- South African, 38% disagreed and 24% neither disagreed nor agreed. Both studies seem to have their respondents supporting imported brands as compared to local products.

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid				
Packaging	32	11.0	13.9	13.9
Quality	146	50.0	63.2	77.1
Price	11	3.8	4.8	81.8
Accessibility	35	12.0	15.2	97.0
Others Specify	6	2.1	2.6	99.6
12	1	.3	.4	100.0
Total	231	79.1	100.0	
Missing				
System	61	20.9		
Total	292	100.0		

Table 4:- Factors Affecting Consumer Buying Behavior

Table 4 above shows the descriptive statistics on the reasons why consumers prefer foreign FMCG's compared to local brands. 50% of respondents cited quality as the main reason they buy imported FMCG's followed by 12.0% who cited accessibility of the FMCG's. 11.0% cited packaging, 3.8% cited price and 2.1% cited other reasons. This study's findings in table 4 are almost similar to other studies done in India, Malaysia, Indonesia and Ghana. These studies found quality to be the most influencing factor to consumer buying preference at 68%, 51% and 59% for India, Malaysia and

Ghana respectively (Dwi & Nyoman, 2020; Sarker & Rahman, 2017; Domie, 2013). In China, quality was followed by packaging at 23% and attitude at 8%. In Malaysia, quality was followed by price (40%), branding (5%), packaging (3%) and others (1%). In Ghana, quality was followed by price (19%) and packaging (17%). A comparative study by Darku & Akpan (2020) in South Africa and Ghana also found that quality, price and design were important factors influencing consumers buying preference with mean scores of 4, 4.46 and 4.2 respectively.

A. Hypothesis Results

Hypothesis Test Summary

	Null Hypothesis	Test	Sig.	Decision
1	The categories of customer awareness occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.
2	The categories of promotional strategies occur with equal probabilities.	One-Sample Chi-Square Test	.000	Reject the null hypothesis.

Asymptotic significances are displayed. The significance level is .050.

a. Lilliefors Corrected

Fig 5:- Hypothesis Test Summary

➤ The level of awareness by the consumers of the local FMCG's (Hypothesis 1)

It was hypothesized that the level of awareness by consumers of the local FMCG's has influence on the consumption and support of local FMCG's in Zambia. The results therefore confirms that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis be accepted that the level of awareness by consumers of the FMCG's positively influences the consumption and support of local FMCG's. The results of the hypothesis test are in agreement with Salehudin (2016) who found that customer awareness to the buy local campaign influences customer support towards local products.

➤ The promotional strategies used to support the local FMCG's (Hypothesis 2)

It was hypothesized that the promotional strategies affect the support the consumption and support of local FMCG's in Zambia (Hypothesis 2). The results therefore confirms that the null hypothesis is rejected and the alternative hypothesis be accepted as evidenced in table 5 that the promotional strategies used to support the implementation of the campaign positively influences the consumption and support of local FMCG's in Zambia. The results of the hypothesis test are in agreement with Darku & Akpan (2020) who found that effective choice of promotional strategies encouraged the spreading of information through word-of-mouth. This enhanced the success of the campaign in Ghana.

B. Cross Tabulation

MEDIA	Have you ever seen the campaign?		TOTAL
	NO	YES	
Where did you see the promotional campaign?			
Billboard	16.5%	83.5%	100%
Newspaper	30.8%	69.2%	100%
Radio	26.1%	73.9%	100%
TV	30%	70%	100%
Non	95%	5%	100%

Table 6:- Where the Customers Saw the Campaign and Whether they have Ever Seen the Campaign

Table 6 above shows the relationships between the media used by the campaign implementers and whether the respondents have ever seen the campaign. Out of 293 respondents, 160 have never seen the campaign on any of the media platforms. 95% respondents have never seen the campaign on any platform, 83.5% respondents have seen the campaign on the Billboard and 16.5% respondents have never seen the campaign on the billboards. The table shows that the total of 180 respondents have never seen the campaign and only 111 have seen the campaign.

IX. CONCLUSION

Dwi & Nyoman (2020) affirmed that there are few studies on the factors that are associated with buying local products in developing nations that includes Zambia when it comes to buying locally made products. Nonetheless, the results of studies on the factors that influence the purchasing of local products in developing nations are comparable to those discovered in developed countries (Arsil, Li, & Bruwer, 2016). The study findings India indicates that consumers of local FMCG's were influenced by quality (68%), attitude (67%), brand related issues (58%) and packaging (23%) (Vijayalakshmi, Gurumoorthy, Lingavel, Arulmozhi, & Kannan, 2020). This study was in agreement with Zariyawati, Norazlina, Annuar, & Manisah (2016) in Malaysia who found that customers were influenced by quality, price and packaging when buying the FMCG's. The local customers continued support of imported FMCG's brands could be as a result of the perceived value they get from the products, of which quality comes out to be the most important determinant when buying FMCG's.

Customers can only buy products which are available to them. The results in table 8 shows that 231 out of 292 (79.1%) respondents buy imported FMCG's brands and only 20.9% buy local brands. The continued support of imported brands could be as results of unavailability and poor quality local FMCG's.

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